

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS ON THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Kenesbayev Adilbay Jenisbay uli

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute, Assistant teacher Uzbekistan, Nukus

E-mail: jasprogrammist96@gmail.com

Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of digital educational platforms on the quality of education. The study examines the possibilities of improving the quality of education through digital resources.

Key words: Interactive tools, digital education, educational and methodological support, multimedia, informatics, digitalization.

INTRODUCTION

The modern educational process is closely linked to digital technologies. Educational platforms offer innovative solutions in the field of pedagogy, serving to make the learning process interactive and convenient. This article analyzes the impact of digital educational platforms on the quality of education and the possibilities of increasing the effectiveness of student learning through them.

The reasons for choosing the topic and its problem. Digital technologies are emerging as an important tool for the effective organization of the educational process in the field of education. However, the implementation of the use of digital platforms in many educational institutions is slow. The adaptation of students and teachers to new technologies, problems related to infrastructure, and insufficient qualifications of teachers are seen as important problems in this area.[1]

The purpose and objectives of the study. The main goal of this research is to determine the impact of digital educational platforms on the quality of education and to improve the methods of their implementation. The research objectives are as follows:

- Identify the advantages of digital platforms in the educational process.
- Studying the experience of students and teachers in using digital platforms.
- Assessment of the impact of platforms on the quality and effectiveness of education.

The novelty or significance of the research. While numerous studies have been conducted on digital educational platforms, this article introduces novelty by analyzing their comprehensive impact on the quality of education, including the possibilities of interactivity, self-control, and an individual approach. At the same time, the study is significant because it was conducted taking into account regional technological limitations.[2]

A brief overview of previous studies and their limitations. Previous studies have highlighted many aspects of integrating digital platforms into the educational process. For example, Anderson and Dron (2011) analyzed three generations of distance learning in their research. Siemens (2005) reflected on the connections between students in the digital environment. However, most of these studies only highlight the technological possibilities and insufficiently show the limitations of their implementation in practice. At the same time, no attention was paid to territorial and infrastructure restrictions. This article aims to address these shortcomings.

Methods

The following methods were used in the study:

Literature review: Scientific articles and statistical data related to digital platforms were studied.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-1

Survey: Students and teachers were surveyed about the effectiveness of digital platforms.

Experimental testing: The lesson process was organized using digital platforms, and the results were compared with traditional methods.[3]

Results

The research results showed that the use of digital platforms affects the quality of education as follows:

<i>Increases engagement:</i>	Students will have the opportunity to gain a deeper understanding and master the material. For example, they can easily learn difficult topics through simulations and video materials.
<i>Individual approach:</i>	Each student will be given the opportunity to develop personalized lesson plans.
<i>Self-control:</i>	Students can independently assess their level of knowledge through tests and other assessment tools.
<i>No time and space restrictions:</i>	Opportunities for distance learning will expand.
<i>Educational efficiency:</i>	According to the survey results, students said that they were 30% more effective in acquiring knowledge through the use of digital platforms.

Let's talk about the use of educational and methodological materials created for the subject "Informatika and Information Technology". This educational and methodological resource is intended for schoolchildren and subject teachers in the 8th grade of general education schools with the subject "Informatika and Information Technologies" taught in the Karakalpak language.

Program title sheet

The homepage has a simple and intuitive interface, allowing quick access to key sections. The user can customize the information on the home page according to their needs, which increases efficiency. The most important sections on the platform (lessons, developments, e-library, tests) open in one tap from the home page. The most up-to-date information, changes and news about the educational process are posted here. The ability to quickly find any lesson development, resource, or topic is very important for users.

Lesson development section

There are lesson plans for teachers and students at the primary, secondary, and advanced levels. The use of video, audio, interactive tests, and graphic materials makes lessons even more interesting. Lesson plans can be downloaded in PDF, DOCX, or PPT formats. Users can comment and evaluate

the quality and effectiveness of lesson developments. Lesson plans are constantly updated in accordance with modern trends and new educational standards.

How to create a website

The website creation section is designed to explain the process of developing a website to students and developers independently. This section covers the main stages of website creation, programming languages, and methods of working with technologies. The section "Stages of Website Preparation" shows the steps that the student must go through in the process of studying website preparation and provides instructions for finding solutions to emerging problems. What is a website and its key components. Frontend and backend concepts. The difference between static and dynamic websites. Creating web pages, tags, and structures in HTML. CSS design, page style adjustment, responsiveness. Add interactive elements in JavaScript, work with events. Domain selection and registration. Hosting services and uploading files. Bringing a website to the web. Using systems such as WordPress, Joomla, and Drupal. Ready-made templates & Plate.[4]

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-1

Website preparation steps section

Discussion

Digital platforms not only make the learning process interactive and convenient, but also create some limitations. For example:

Technological infrastructure: There are problems with the internet and technological devices in a number of regions.

Teacher Training: Teachers are not always able to fully utilize digital technologies.

Adaptation difficulties: The level of student learning requires rapid adaptation to the digital environment.

However, it has been found that the positive aspects of digital platforms outweigh the negative aspects. In the future, it is necessary to expand the technological capabilities of digital educational platforms and improve the qualifications of teachers.[5]

Conclusion

Digital educational platforms are an important tool for improving the quality of education. They enable the learning process to be interactive, flexible, and user-friendly. The research results show that digital platforms increase the effectiveness of students' learning and improve the learning process. Therefore, it is very important to further expand the implementation of these platforms and develop strategies for their application.[6]

REFERENCES

1. Kh, A. M. Advantages of using e-learning resources in preschool education. International journal for Innovative Engineering and Management Research, 9, 5-9.
2. Ilyasova Z. K. bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf informatika o'qituvchilarini kasbiy tayyorlashning muhim xususiyatlar // Innovations in Technology and Science Education. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 15. – C. 99-105.
3. Quatbaevich, Kunnazarov Amangeldi. "METHODOLOGY OF CREATING AND USING SOFTWARE TOOLS IN COMPUTER SCIENCE." (2023).
4. Juginisova, J. I. (2025). USING SOFTWARE TOOLS IN TEACHING CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 5(1), 170-173.
5. Kenesbaevna, I. Z. (2023). Characteristics of Teaching Theoretical Foundations of Informatics in the System of Pedagogical Higher Education. International Journal on Integrated Education, 4(11), 142-145.
6. Ataxanovich, M. U., Rajabboy o'g'li, Q. D., & Abdullayevich, A. M. (2021). Use of visit karakalpakstan mobile app in the development of tourism in the republic of karakalpakstan. International Journal of Human Computing Studies, 3(8), 13-17.